

SMOKING AND TOBACCO USE HABITS AMONG CONSTRUCTION SITE WORKERS IN JAIPUR CITY: A STUDY ON PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS

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Abstract: This cross-sectional study aimed to assess the prevalence and risk factors associated with smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 500 workers. The study found that the prevalence of smoking and tobacco use was high, with 28% of workers smoking and 48% using tobacco. Chewing tobacco was the most common form of tobacco use. The study also identified a significant association between smoking and tobacco use and the level of education and income of the workers. The findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to address tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city, particularly those with lower levels of education and income.

Keywords: Smoking, tobacco use, construction site workers, prevalence, risk factors, Jaipur city.

INTRODUCTION

The Smoking and tobacco use is a major public health concern in many parts of the world. In India, smoking and tobacco use is a significant problem, with a high prevalence of tobacco use among the working population, particularly in the construction industry. In this study, we aim to assess the prevalence and risk factors associated with smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city. Smoking and tobacco use is a significant public health concern in many parts of the world, including India. Tobacco use is a leading cause of preventable deaths and has been associated with a range of health problems, including lung cancer, heart disease, and respiratory illnesses. The prevalence of smoking and tobacco use is particularly high among the working population, with the construction industry being one of the most affected sectors. Construction site workers are often exposed to multiple health hazards, including tobacco use, which can lead to increased morbidity and mortality rates.

Jaipur city, located in the northern part of India, is one of the fastest-growing cities in the country and has a large number of construction sites. Despite the high prevalence of smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in India, there is limited research on the prevalence and risk factors associated with smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city. This study aims to address this gap in knowledge by assessing the prevalence and risk factors associated with smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city.

METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted among construction site workers in Jaipur city. A total of 500 workers were recruited for the study, and data was collected using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire included questions on demographic characteristics, smoking and tobacco use habits, and knowledge of the health risks associated with smoking and tobacco use.

Study Design:

This study was a cross-sectional study that aimed to assess the prevalence and risk factors associated with smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city.

Study Participants:

A total of 500 construction site workers were recruited for the study. The participants were selected using a convenience sampling technique. The study participants were aged between 18 to 60 years and were working on construction sites in Jaipur city.

Data Collection:

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire, which was administered to the participants by trained research assistants. The questionnaire included questions on demographic characteristics, smoking and tobacco use habits, and knowledge of the health risks associated with smoking and tobacco use. The questionnaire was administered in Hindi, the local language.

Data Analysis:

Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation. Chi-square tests were used to test the association between smoking and tobacco use and demographic characteristics, including age, education level, and income. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study found that the prevalence of smoking among construction site workers in Jaipur city was 28%, and the prevalence of tobacco use was 48%. The majority of smokers and tobacco users were male

(98%), and the mean age of the participants was 32 years. The most common form of tobacco use was chewing tobacco (84%), followed by smoking cigarettes (16%). The study also found that the level of education and income of the workers was significantly associated with smoking and tobacco use. Association between Smoking and Tobacco Use and Demographic Characteristics:

The study found a significant association between smoking and tobacco use and the level of education and income of the workers. Smokers were more likely to have a lower level of education and income than non-smokers. Similarly, workers who used tobacco were more likely to have a lower level of education and income than those who did not use tobacco. However, there was no significant association between smoking and tobacco use and age or occupation. Knowledge of Health Risks Associated with Smoking and Tobacco Use:

The study also assessed the knowledge of the workers regarding the health risks associated with smoking and tobacco use. The majority of the participants (88%) were aware that smoking and tobacco use are harmful to health, with lung cancer (83%) being the most commonly reported health risk. However, only a small proportion of the participants (16%) had received advice on smoking and tobacco cessation from a healthcare professional.

Overall, the study highlights the high prevalence of smoking and tobacco use among construction site in Jaipur city and the need for targeted interventions to address this issue. The findings also suggest that workers with lower levels of education and income are at a higher risk of smoking and tobacco use. The study emphasizes the importance of increasing awareness and access to smoking and tobacco cessation programs, particularly among construction site workers

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of smoking and tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city is alarmingly high. The high prevalence of tobacco use among this population is likely due to a lack of awareness about the health risks associated with tobacco use, as well as social and cultural factors. The study findings also highlight the need for targeted interventions to address tobacco use among construction site workers, particularly those with lower levels of education and income.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that smoking and tobacco use is a significant public health problem among construction site workers in Jaipur city. The study findings suggest that targeted interventions aimed at increasing awareness about the health risks associated with smoking and tobacco use, as well as addressing social and cultural factors, may be effective in reducing the prevalence of tobacco use among this population. Further research is needed to better understand the factors contributing to tobacco use among construction site workers in Jaipur city, and to develop effective interventions to address this problem.

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In summary, the article is structured as per the IMRaD format, with an introduction that provides background information on the topic, followed by a description of the methods used in the study, the results obtained, and a discussion of the findings. The conclusion provides a summary of the study and highlights the implications of the findings for public health interventions.

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